

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

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Abstract	This report focuses in two axes of COVID-X Programme; firstly, it gathers the key results from the COVID-X Open Calls 1 and 2, and, secondly, it provides the COVID-X community building action results.
Keywords	Business Acceleration, Community Building, Open Calls, Outreach.

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
 OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In 2021, COVID-X Programme has planned, implemented, and evaluated two Open Calls to select and fund 30+ European SMES or Start-Ups tackling clinical challenges COVID-19 with data – and AI-driven innovative technologies. All the selected solutions, that are either single solutions validating their system with a COVID-X Pilot Site or team solutions validating the innovation with a third-party healthcare partner, join the COVID-X Acceleration Programme organized by the [COVID-X Project](#)¹ in two waves of 10-months. All third parties will benefit not only from direct funding (up to 150K€ / solutions) but also from tailored business, ethical and technical mentoring sessions that the COVID-X consortium experts provide. The key objective is to boost the quick market update of the funded solutions, to overcome COVID-19 with the power of health data.

The COVID-X project is funded in the scope of the call H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B² and involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from seven different countries:

FIGURE 1. COVID-X PROJECT PARTNERS LOGOTYPES

The first Open Call, running for eight weeks until 27th of January 2021, obtained 122 applications from 29 different countries. After an evaluation process, combining internal and external evaluation committees, 16 solutions that met the set eligibility criteria, essentially the TRL 7+ and CE marking requirements, got selected in the first batch for a total of 2 200 000 € of funding granted for European third parties. These teams join the COVID-X Acceleration Programme from April until December 2021.

After the experiences of the first open call, the second open call was decided to run in two stages, helping to select the top-notch candidates and target the fit solutions even better. The 1st stage of the OC#2, running for seven weeks from early June until the 22nd of July 2021, attracted a total of 79 applications from 24 European countries. After an internal eligibility screening and evaluations, 39 applications were invited to apply for the 2nd stage, that ran from the 7th of August until the 16th of September 2021, resulting in 37 submitted applications. The selected solutions will be announced by the end of October 2021, and they will join the COVID-X Acceleration programme from November 2021 until July 2022.

The Communication Strategy, developed in the first project month, was a crucial part for the Open Calls success, enabling the project to reach out to a critical mass of the target groups. In the promotion of both open calls, the outreach plan included a mixed portfolio of promotional activities, namely

¹ <https://www.covid-x.eu/>

² https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B

continuous social media presence in LinkedIn and Twitter, targeted one-to-one message campaigns, press releases and publications on online media, and various newsletters. In addition, the series of targeted webinars hosted by F6S offered occasions for interested applications to interact directly with the COVID-X team.

Community Building is a central part of COVID-X project with two key objectives: on one hand, it focuses on engaging with stakeholders from the different COVID-X target groups, helping to raise interest in the COVID-X open calls. And, on the other hand, it aims at creating synergies with similar initiatives to leverage even further the impact of the funded solutions in COVID-X Acceleration Programme, especially for their market access and visibility.

During the first project year, the COVID-X project scouted and interacted with a varied range of stakeholders including European data-driven technology companies and healthcare providers taking care of coronavirus patients (i.e., primary target groups) as well as innovation & health ecosystems, citizens and patients and the European Commission (i.e., secondary target groups). These community building activities have resulted in good visibility of the COVID-X Programme in the sectors of digital transformation of healthcare (among EIT Health, ECHAlliance, related H2020 projects, varied online media etc.) and in creation of a dynamic community directly including 16 SMEs and 13 Healthcare providers (from OC#1) - and more to be onboarded from OC#2 -, collaboration with 20+ H2020 projects dealing with COVID-19 or challenges of pandemics.

During the second project year, the stakeholder engagement focus will shift from promoting the COVID-X Open Calls towards spreading out the results from the Acceleration Programme and boosting the public visibility of the COVID-X Game Changer solutions. The stakeholder engagement strategy will continue following the agile framework enabling to adjust the actions according to the immediate needs coming from the project or the stakeholders. The objective is to grow the COVID-X community with tailored stakeholder engagement actions, which leverages the COVID-X Acceleration Programme impact especially for the funded solutions that are ready to enter the digital healthcare markets.

The current document reports the actions taken, and outcomes achieved in relation to the promotional strategies during the first period of the project. It also outlines the Agile Stakeholder Management strategy and includes relevant statistics and findings from the open calls. The current version will be updated and submitted on M24, under the name D3.5 CovidInnovation Final Report, and will describe the implemented actions during the second period of the project.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND NOTIONS

TERM / EXPRESSION	DEFINITION
COVID-X Consortium or Consortium	Set of legal entities that are cumulatively responsible to implement the COVID-X project as defined in the Grant Agreement for project number 101016065
Beneficiary or 3rd Party	An SME or a consortium of an SME and Healthcare provider, led by an SME that submitted a proposal to the acceleration programme which was accepted to be funded, and have signed, or are in the process of signing, a sub-grant agreement.
Solution	Projects carried out by 3 rd parties (outside COVID-X Consortium) that benefit from the COVID-X funding and join the COVID-X Acceleration Programme. The solutions can be either single or team solutions.
Single Player / Solution	A third-party project carried out by a technology SME or Start-Up and validated with one COVID-X clinical partner.
Team Player / Solution	A third-party project carried out by a team of a technology SME or Start-Up and healthcare provider disposing clinical data of coronavirus patients. The solution is validated within the team.
Game Changers	All third-party projects selected and funded in the COVID-X Acceleration Programme Open Calls #1 and #2.
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
External Evaluator	Expert hired by the consortium to assist in the evaluation of proposals. External evaluators cannot have conflicts of interest and are bound by a confidentiality agreement.
Internal evaluation committee	Set of at least three appropriately qualified experts from the consortium, representing the clinical, technical, and business perspectives, who are assigned the responsibility of performing evaluations in any stage of the acceleration programme.
Mentor	Person from the consortium who works closely with the beneficiary to foster communication with the consortium and assess progress of the project. The mentor may be part of an evaluation committee.

1 Statistics and findings on the Open Calls

The COVID-X project aims to provide competitive and market oriented European SMEs access to **knowledge, technology, capital, and markets**, aiming to place new products and services in the market to fight against the COVID-19 pandemic. COVID-X funds EU SMEs and Healthcare Providers to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up. The funding is being invested in 30+ products with TRL 7+ and [or in the process of] CE marking, covering two profiles:

- **Single players** EU Tech SMEs / Start-Ups validating their solutions at one of COVID-X clinical partners (KI, SERMAS or ICH).
- **Team players:** Tech Provider working with a Healthcare provider that will validate the solution.

The 30 selected solutions join the COVID-X Acceleration programme, obtaining direct funding (100 000 € for single solutions and 150 000 € team solutions) and accessing the 9-month mentoring programme running in three Sprints. The solutions benefit from mentoring provided by COVID-X Community's experts including support in technical, Ethical, and business development of their products / services. Moreover, all selected third-party technology providers integrate their solutions with the COVID-X Sandbox. The ambition of COVID-X is to streamline the deployment and techno-economic validation of the solutions in the fight against COVID-19.

To select the 30 solutions joining the COVID-X Programme, the project ran two open calls in 2021. The following subsections detail the implemented methodology and stakeholder engagement for both open calls and provide an overview of the key results from the open calls. F6S (as leader of task 3.1 Open Call management) oversaw implementing and managing both open calls with continuous support from AUS, leading the communication (Task 3.2 Communication & Outreach) and managing and amplifying the ecosystem dynamics (Task 3.3 Community Building) as well as from BOSONIT leading WP4 CovidProgramme.

1.1 Open Call 1

The Open Call 1 ran for eight weeks from early December 2020 until the 27th January 2021. In total, 122 applications were submitted from data technology companies and healthcare providers coming from 29 different countries in Europe and beyond. 16 solutions met the eligibility criteria, and were selected to join the COVID-X Acceleration Programme after an internal and external evaluation process. Out of the 16 solutions, 13 solutions are team players and three are single players.

1.1.1 Application Process

As shown in *Figure 2*, once the Open Call 1 applications were closed on 21st January 2021, the selection and onboarding of the selected solutions ran until the end of March 2021. The kick-off bootcamp onboarding the 16 successful projects in the COVID-X Programme was hosted on the 12th April 2021.

FIGURE 2: OPEN CALL 1 ACCELERATION PROCESS TIMELINE

The **application guidelines**, written by F6S, gather all essential information for the potential applicants about the eligibility criteria, selection process, and contracting. These guidelines were published on the COVID-X Website³ on a page dedicated to the Open Call #1. These remain available in open access via Zenodo⁴. The applicants consulted and submitted **the application form (see D3.2 First Call of Startups/SMEs documentation)** and connected annexes via the F6S platform⁵.

1.1.2 OC#1 promotion and stakeholder engagement

During the 8-week Open Call 1 opening, to attract potential applications, the COVID-X partners focused on promoting the call among maximum number of European stakeholders targeting European ICT SMEs and Start-Ups with services / solutions on eHealth markets, European healthcare providers (hospitals, clinics, medical universities, primary care centres) as well as varied innovation ecosystems engaged in digital transformation of health, namely the EIT Health and varied Digital Innovation Hubs. This section describes the actions taken to reach out the target groups and the key results of this proactive stakeholder engagement. In addition, all produced communication items remain available in open access via Zenodo and the links to download these are provided in the related sections of this sub-chapter.

COVID-X Website

The project website is the main resource for generic promotion of the project activities and results to all target audiences, providing comprehensive information about the COVID-X Programme, its objectives, the two open calls and the project news and outcomes. The first version was ready in November 2020 (M01), and ever since, the website structure and contents are updated regularly based on the ongoing project activities. Moreover, its design is mobile-friendly to be displayed on different devices, assuring quick loading times, accessibility, tracking of web analytics traffic, search engine optimization and integration with relevant social media platforms.

³ www.covid-x.eu

⁴ https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_OC1_Guidelines

⁵ www.f6s.com/covid-x/connect

FIGURE 3: PROJECT WEBSITE HOMEPAGE PRINTSCREEN

The website is a powerful tool to engage with stakeholders, informing them about the work in the COVID-X Programme in terms of deliverables, Open Calls, selected solutions (called Game Changers) and project updates. Between December 2020 and January 2021, when the OC#1 was running, the website recorded 237 monthly visits (for more information about the generated traffic, see Figure 4).

FIGURE 4: COVID-X WEBSITE TRAFFIC DURING OC1 DEC 20- JAN21

Social media channels

The COVID-X Programme has built its online presence in several social media channels, with particular focus on Twitter and LinkedIn. These channels have proven to be the most effective platforms when interacting with research and innovation communities, spreading out new publications and participation in different events. In addition, in LinkedIn, a dedicated matchmaking group was created to support the Open Call applicants to connect and submit applications for team solutions.

Furthermore, the project also set up Facebook and YouTube accounts. The Facebook page was created due to the numerous visits COVID-X website gets from this social media channel. COVID-X YouTube channel was created to host the webinars to be embedded on the website.

While posting on social media, the COVID-X team uses specific hashtags, supporting the virtual identity of the project, for the project related posts, e.g. #GameOn #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX. When posting about the selected solutions from OC#1, the hashtag #GameChangers is also used in all the posts.

Between October 2020 and January 2021, the COVID-X Programme achieved a group of regular followers on the dedicated social media channels:

TABLE 1: SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS RESUME

Social Media Channels	Link	#followers/members
Twitter account	https://twitter.com/TheCovidX	331 followers
LinkedIn Company page	www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/	230 followers
LinkedIn Matchmaking group	www.linkedin.com/groups/12493790/	63 members

During the Open Call #1 Promotion Campaign, the COVID-X project asked the stakeholders to share the related posts in their social media, mainly on Twitter and LinkedIn. The COVID-X Open Calls Posts got re-shared over 60 times by different stakeholders (see Figure 5 as an example).

FIGURE 5: EXAMPLE OF A RE-POST OF THE OC#1 ANNOUNCEMENT ON SOCIAL MEDIA

One-to-one messages

One of the most efficient ways to potential applicants in the open calls are targeted one-to-one messages via email campaigns. AUS team created a database of stakeholders from the specific target groups, including information on organization, field of activity and contact details. This database was used for the Open Call promotion campaign via one-to-one messages and in total over 800 direct messages were sent out to attract attention to the open call, including messages to:

- 390+ innovation & health ecosystems
- 50 healthcare providers
- 240+ European technology SMES and Start-Ups
- 20 publishing platforms
- 70+ European Enterprise Network contacts
- 106 H2020 ICT & Health National Contact points

As mentioned in the previous section, these stakeholders were requested to support the project and spread the open call announcement within their organization, networks, and social media.

Press Releases

To reach out to a broader audience and encourage public sharing of the open call, the COVID-X Programme has published and promoted two press releases regarding the Open Call 1 publication:

- November 2020 PR about the kick-off of the COVID-X Programme: 308 downloads⁶

⁶ https://zenodo.org/record/4560094/files/COVID-X%20_Press%20Release_Nov2020.pdf?download=1

- December 2020 PR about the launch of Open Call 1: 50 downloads⁷

FIGURE 6: THE 1ST COVID-X PRESS RELEASE

In addition, the project benefited from the COVID-X consortium, especially the clinical partners, timely press releases published individually for their network of customers and members to promote the open call.

Slide Deck & One pager

Digital slide decks and one-pagers are eye-catching elements to quickly draw attention and share the vision and objectives of the project, sometimes integrated with other campaigns (social media).

One slide deck⁸ (see Figure 7) and a flyer⁹ (see Figure 8) were created to promote the open call.

FIGURE 7: OPEN CALL 1 FLYER

⁷ https://zenodo.org/record/4560110/files/COVID-X%20Press%20Release_Dec2020.pdf?download=1

⁸ https://zenodo.org/record/4560131/files/COVID-X_Slide_Deck.pdf?download=1

⁹ https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Flyer

FINANCIAL SUPPORT & VALIDATION

- Direct funding for 30+ Data Technology Solutions ready-to-market
- Products will be validated in real-world clinical sites and must have CE marking - or in the process to be certified.

FIGURE 8: ILLUSTRATION OF THE SLIDE DECK FOR OPEN CALL 1

Newsletters

Complementary to email engagement, COVID-X partners used different existing newsletters to spread online the Open Call #1 and invitations to the related webinars. Moreover, three COVID-X partners released a newsletter promoted the OC#1: Civitta, Bosonit and Humanitas. The COVID-X programme OC#1 was also promoted through the Innovation Procurement Newsletter of the EC newsletter¹⁰ (see Figure 9).

FIGURE 9: OC 1 ANNOUNCEMENT IN THE EC INNOVATION PROCUREMENT NEWSLETTER

Webinars

The project hosted a series of three webinars presenting the open call, clinical partners, challenges, technical implementation and requirements for the COVID-X Sandbox. During these sessions, the participants were able to ask questions to the partners regarding the application process. All three webinars (named OC#1 1st, 2nd, and 3rd webinar) were recorded and remain openly accessible via COVID-X YouTube channel¹¹ allowing applicants to consult after the actual webinar.

¹⁰<https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/newsletter-archives/29379>

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZg26pyMWFUfjiulukh-lg/videos>

One-to-one meetings

Meetings are successful when targeting very specific key individuals, often as a follow-up of an email exchange or an event. For the scope of the project, this is especially relevant when reaching out to clinical partners interested in the methodology, and innovation ecosystems with the capacity to amplify the outreach of the open calls. During the promotion of the OC#1, the COVID-X team had several meetings to leverage awareness about the project and to promote the OC#1: Coordination meeting with INNO4COV-19¹², CoronaVirus-2020-2B Projects meeting¹³, EU Meeting with INNO4COV-19 and COVID-X¹⁴, Presentation of the COVID-X project at the eHealth Network¹⁵, Coordination with INNO4COV-19¹⁶, CoronaVirus-2020-2B Projects meeting¹⁷.

Events and conferences

To leverage the opportunity and spread the word about the COVID-X OC#1, certain project partners attended two conferences:

- Nicosia Risk Forum 2020 - Preparing for the Next Pandemic – the important role of Civil Protection: A Regional view. Covid-X: leveraging technological innovations to fight the pandemic¹⁸.
- The Instituto Pedro Nunes, 2nd Seminar - From Cloud to the Ground¹⁹.

1.1.3 Evaluation Process

Once closed on the 27th January 2021, the OC#1 evaluation process was started and managed by F6S. This process included the following steps:

- **Eligibility check:** assessing if the proposals met the administrative conditions to apply to the programme. All 112 applications went through this process.
- **Pre-screening:** performing quality check and assessing the project alignment with the goals of the COVID-X project, especially the implemented technology, clinical challenge and TRL7+ level. 10 applications passing the eligibility check were pre-screened.
- **Remote evaluation:** ranking the 36 proposals passing the pre-screening phase by an external evaluation committee formed by six external members (see Table 2).
- **Online interview:** providing top 36 applicants the opportunity of detailing how their solutions provide the impact expected and how they can benefit from the acceleration programme.
- **Consensus meeting and matchmaking:** assigning the three selected single solutions to internal healthcare providers and select team solutions.

¹² 04.11.2020 Partner: F6S

¹³ 28.10.2020 Partner: F6S

¹⁴ 11.11.2020 Partner: F6S

¹⁵ 13.11.2020 Partner: F6S

¹⁶ 09.12.2020 Partner: F6S

¹⁷ 29.04.2021 Partners: F6S & AUS

¹⁸ 26.11.2020 Partner involved: CIV <https://cerides.euc.ac.cy/nicosia-risk-forum/nicosia-risk-forum-2020/>

¹⁹ 17.12.2020 Partner involved: F6S <https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2756?uri=%2Fnoticias%3Ftema%3D7>

TABLE 2: OPEN CALL 1 EXTERNAL EVALUATORS

First Name and Name	Position	Organization
Antonio Lindo da Cunha	Executive Director of Automation Lab	Instituto Pedro Nunes
Nuno Seixas	Head of Quality and Operational Excellence	PT Inovação – Altice Labs
Ana Vila	IP Exploitation & Knowledge Transfer	International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory
Marco de la Feld	Expert evaluator	European Commission
Tiago Rua	COVID-19 vaccination: Programme Manager	Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust
Fabrizio Bellina	Marketing & Customer Innovation Manager	Roche

1.1.4 OC#1 Results

In total, 112 applications were submitted, and 36 applications went through the evaluation, resulting in 16 selected top-notch projects out of which three are single solutions and 13 are team solutions. All selected solutions focus on a specific clinical challenge in diagnosis, prognosis, or follow-up of COVID-19 patients, as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: OPEN CALL 1 ADDRESSED CLINICAL CHALLENGES

Clinical Challenge		Number of Selected Solutions Addressing it
Diagnosis	#1 Early Detection	3
	#2 Innovative Diagnostics	3
Prognosis	#3 Personalized Care	2
	#4 Remote Care	5
Follow-up	#5 Healthcare Continuity	0
	#6 Recovery	1
Open Challenge (only for team solutions)		2

The onboarded solutions come from 29 different organizations, including both start-ups, SMEs, and healthcare providers, from 11 European member states covering the Northern Regions (Finland, Estonia, and Denmark), Central Europe (Netherlands, Luxembourg, France, Belgium, and Austria) and the Southern Countries (Italy, Spain, and Greece).

The funded innovative data-driven solutions combine AI with different technologies, namely voice processing, natural language processing or biomarkers, with the common aim to support healthcare professionals in delivering more efficient care for coronavirus-patients.

TABLE 4: FUNDED APPLICATIONS UNDER OPEN CALL #1

Title	Solution Type	Partner Name (s)	Addressed Challenge	Accorded Grant (€)
SEGTNAN	SS	Synaptic ApS (Denmark)	#2 Innovative Diagnostics	100 000 €
CAPTAIN-X	SS	Capitain Coach P.C. (Greece)	#4 Remote Care	100 000 €
LOMT	SS	Jetware SRL (Italy)	#2 Innovative Diagnostics	100 000 €
COVID-19 TRIAGE	TS	Symptoma GmbH (Austria), Claudiana - Provincial High School of Health (Italy)	#1 Early Detection	150 000 €
C-ARM	TS	Softbrik (Estonia), AyurVaid (India – not granted)	#1 Early Detection	100 000 €
COV-ART	TS	Bio Logbook (France), The University Hospital of Liège (Belgium)	#3 Personalized Care	150 000 €
DDRehab	TS	Ab.Acus srl (Italy), The Valduce Hospital - Villa Beretta (Italy)	#6 Recovery	150 000 €
KCOVRI	TS	KAMU Health Ltd (Finland), Finnish Lung Health Association (FILHA) (Finland)	#Open Challenge	150 000 €
Gaston scholar	TS	Medical Decision Support systems B.V. (Netherlands), Catharina Hospital (Netherlands)	#2 Innovative Diagnostics	150 000 €
VADI	TS	VoiceMed sarl (Luxembourg), National Laboratory of Health (LNS) (Luxembourg)	#1 Early Detection	150 000 €
Covid@home	TS	BeWell Innovations NV (Belgium), Maria Middelaes General Hospital (Belgium)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
MADCAP	TS	AVATR srl (Italy), University Hospital Mater Domini of Catanzaro (Italy)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
TRAJECT	TS	Amalfi Analytics, S.L. (Italy), Health Management Foundation of the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau (Spain)	#3 Personalized Care	150 000 €

Title	Solution Type	Partner Name (s)	Addressed Challenge	Accorded Grant (€)
Healthantia Care4Covid	TS	Innovation Sprint Sprl (Belgium), Agostino Gemelli IRCCS University Hospital Foundation (Italy)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
AVIATE	TS	Vidavo S.A (Greece), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) (Greece)	#Open Challenge	150 000 €
C@H	TS	Business and Bytes Ltd. (Greece,) Private Medical Clinic on Vascular Research (Vascular Research SA) (Greece)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
Total amount of funding granted in the Open Call #1				2 200 000 €

An infographic (see Figure 10) was created to disseminate the Open Call 1 results via COVID-X social media channels and the project website, it can be downloaded online²⁰. All 16 solutions follow the COVID-X Acceleration Programme, organized under WP4 CovidProgramme, until the end of December 2021, and they are considered as COVID-X Game Changers in the COVID-X Community.

FIGURE 10: OVERVIEW OF OPEN CALL 1 RESULT

²⁰ https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Infographic_OC1

1.2 Open Call 2

The Open Call #2, running for seven weeks from early June until the 22nd July 2021, attracted applications from a varied range of Start-Ups and SMEs around Europe, resulting in 79 final submitted applications (43 single solutions from tech companies and 36 team solutions gathering a tech company and a healthcare provider). The applications came in from 24 European countries and the successful ones are being announced by the end of October 2021.

1.2.1 Application process

To increase the number of applications meeting the set eligibility criteria, essentially in terms of technology readiness levels close to market adoption, the COVID-X team decided to organize the Open Call 2 in two stages (see Figure 3):

- **Stage 1** ran for seven weeks from early June until 22nd July 2021. All 79 received applications were evaluated by the COVID-X consortium to perform an eligibility check and to validate the applications to apply in Stage 2. 39 applications met the eligibility criteria and were qualified to apply in Stage 2.
- **Stage 2** ran from 7th August until 16th September 2021 resulting in 37 submitted applications.

FIGURE 11: OPEN CALL 2 ACCELERATION PROCESS TIMELINE

The OC#2 **Guidelines for Applicants**, written by BOSONIT, AUS and F6S, gather all essential information for the potential applicants about the eligibility criteria, selection process, and contracting, and were published on the COVID-X Website (www.covid-x.eu/) on a page dedicated to the Open Call #2. These remain available in open access via Zenodo²¹. The applicants consulted and submitted **the application form** and the connected annexes (see D3.3 Second Call of Startups/ SMEs documentation) via the F6S platform (<https://www.f6s.com/covid-x/connect>).

1.2.2 OC#2 promotion and stakeholder engagement

The OC2 Stage 1 ran for seven weeks during which an important communication campaign took place to attract applicants from the target groups in all member states. The targeted stakeholders remained the same as in Open Call 1, and the OC#2 communication was built upon the efforts undertaken already for Open Call 1, leveraging the action even further (i.e., increased numbers in terms of reached audiences and communication channels).

²¹ https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_OC2_Guidelines_for_Applicants

COVID-X Website

During the promotion of OC#2, the COVID-X website focussed on promoting the general overview, technical and clinical webinars held by the partners of the project. The Program page was updated explaining the OC#2 timeline, the two-staged application process and providing access to the application guidelines and platform. Between June and September 2021, when the OC#2 was running, the website recorded 190 monthly visitors (for more information about the generated traffic, see Figure 12).

FIGURE 12: COVID-X WEBSITE TRAFFIC DURING OC2 FROM JUNE - SEPTEMBER 2021

Social media channels

During the promotion of the COVID-X OC#2, the social media posts focused on attracting new SMEs and healthcare providers to apply, helping the audience understand the objectives of the programme, and the major changes in the Open Call application process from OC#1 to OC#2. Between June and September 2021, when the OC#2 was running, the number of COVID-X followers in social media increased significantly:

- Twitter: 155 new followers, counting a total of 745 followers (see Figure 13).
- LinkedIn: 105 new followers. Resulting a total of 490 Followers (see Figure 14).
- LinkedIn Matchmaking group gained 30 members from June 2021 until August 2021 (93 member in total, see Figure 15).

FIGURE 13: COVID-X TWITTER FOLLOWERS IN SEPT 2021

FIGURE 14: COVID-X LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS IN SEPT 21

FIGURE 15: COVID-X MATCHMAKING GROUP IN LINKEDIN

During the OC#2 Promotion Campaign, the COVID-X project asked the stakeholders to share the open call related posts in their social media, mainly Twitter and LinkedIn. The COVID-X Open Calls Posts got re-shared over 60 times by different stakeholders (Figure 5 as an example).

FIGURE 16: EXAMPLE OF A RE-POST OF THE OC#2 ANNOUNCEMENT IN SOCIAL MEDIA

One-to-one messages

As in the open call 1 promotion, the COVID-X team did an important one-to-one message campaign to spread the information about the Open Call 2. The first message wave was sent out during the first week after the publication of the OC#2 in June targeting the different COVID-X stakeholders. The stakeholder database created for the OC#1 was enriched with new scouted contacts, a common effort from all COVID-X partners. In total, 1100+ one-to-one messages were sent to inform stakeholders about the open call, including messages to:

- 430+ innovation & health ecosystems
- 120+ healthcare providers
- 350+ technology SMES / Start-Ups
- 30+ European publishing platforms
- 110+ European Enterprise Network contacts
- 130+ H2020 ICT & Health National Contact points

In the messages, the stakeholders received the OC#2 flyer and were requested to spread the open call within their organizations and networks and via their social media channels, as specified in the previous section.

Press Releases

To reach out to a broader audience, the project published a press release about the Open Call 2 in June 2021. The Press Release counts 68 downloads in open access on Zenodo²² (see Figure 17).

FIGURE 17: COVID-X OC#2 PR IN OPEN ACCESS

Slide Deck & One pager

The COVID-X digital slide deck²³ and one-pager²⁴, created for the OC#1, were updated to the new deadlines to quickly draw attention to the new Open Call. The slide deck was used as a baseline in the Open Call webinar presentations, and the one-pager was shared in the one-to-one messaging campaigns.

FIGURE 18: OC#2 ONE-PAGER FLYER

22 https://zenodo.org/record/4899043/files/COVID-X%20_OC2_Press%20Release_June2021.pdf?download=1

23 https://zenodo.org/record/4898994/files/COVID-X_OC2_Slide_Deck.pdf?download=1

24 https://zenodo.org/record/4899128/files/COVID-X_OC2_Flyer.pdf?download=1

Newsletters

The OC#2 was promoted in total of 12 different European newsletters published by external stakeholders, including the following:

- Start-Ups Weekly newsletter²⁵ counting 54.000 subscribers in Europe and beyond.
- ECHAlliance Newsletter in June²⁶ counting 16.500 experts in the community
- Upgraded - Health Startup Association of Finland²⁷
- Scale-Up.eu newsletter²⁸
- AI4EU H2020 project newsletter²⁹
- Startup Eu Strategy White Paper on Scaling Startups Globally³⁰
- Startup Eu Strategy White Paper on Female Entrepreneurship³¹
- STAMINA H2020 project newsletter³²
- Impact Hub external newsletter³³
- Impact Hub Madrid newsletter³⁴
- Call4Europe Newsletter³⁵
- ECHAlliance newsletter in July³⁶

Webinars

As a part of the Open Call 2 campaign, a series of four webinars were organized by F6S with participation of all partners to respond to applicants' open questions. These four sessions included:

- COVID-X OC#2 General Overview
- OC#2 and technical requirements related to COVID-X Sandbox³⁷
- Session about the clinical challenges and requirements³⁸
- General overview and the application requirements³⁹

²⁵ 18.06.2021

²⁶ 22.06.2021 <https://echalliance.com/echalliance-june-2021-newsletter/>

²⁷ 24.06.2021 <https://mailchi.mp/eeff60126917/89ur3syk0f-4767326>

²⁸ June 2021 <https://mailchi.mp/ef7339a59926/the-big-buzz-6>

²⁹ June 2021

³⁰ June 2021 <https://mailchi.mp/deep-ecosystems/white-paper-scaling-startups-globally?e=77698240e4>

³¹ June 2021 <https://mailchi.mp/deep-ecosystems/strategy-white-paper-female-entrepreneurship?e=77698240e4>

³² June 2021

³³ June 2021 <https://mailchi.mp/impacthub/global-ext-newsletter-july2021>

³⁴ June 2021

³⁵ June 2021

³⁶ July 2021 <https://echalliance.com/funding-collaboration-opportunities-for-member-only-september-2021/>

³⁷ www.covid-x.eu/news/learn-about-the-technical-requirements-with-this-webinar-and-apply-to-oc2/

³⁸ www.covid-x.eu/news/meet-the-covid-x-clinical-partners-and-learn-about-the-data-sets-apply-to-oc2/

³⁹ www.covid-x.eu/news/last-oc2-covid-x-webinar-get-an-overview-of-the-programme-and-apply-before-the-22nd-of-july/

As the OC#1 webinars, all these sessions were recorded remain available on COVID-X YouTube channel⁴⁰.

Meetings

AUS represented the COVID-X Programme in two meetings to promote the OC#2: CoronaVirus-2020-2B Projects meeting, including a presentation of COVID-X Open Call 2 and the related Communication Strategy⁴¹ as well as the PREPARE Cluster Meeting⁴².

1.2.3 Evaluation process

In line with the two-stage application process, the Open Call 2 Evaluation Process (see Figure 19) was performed in two phases including internal and external evaluations:

- **Stage 1 - Eligibility check** was carried out by the F6S team to discard all non-eligible proposals that do not meet all the eligibility criteria.
- **Stage 1 - Internal evaluation** of all solutions passing the eligibility check was conducted by the internal evaluation committee composed of one representative of each partner domain (business, technical and clinical partners).
- **Stage 2 - External remote evaluation** was performed by a group of external evaluators assessing the submitted application documents (see Table 5) from 17th September 2021 to 1st October 2021.
- **Stage 2 - Online interviews took place** on 4th and 6th October 2021. During this phase, the best ranked Stage 2 applications (from the external evaluation) were invited in project teams to pitch their solutions to the COVID-X evaluators, who could ask questions about unclear points of the applications.
- **Results are announced by the end of October 2021**, which collides with the submission of this report.

FIGURE 19: OPEN CALL 2 EVALUATION PROCESS

⁴⁰ www.youtube.com/channel/UCZg26pyMWfEufJiulukh-Ig/videos

⁴¹ 29.04.2021 Partners: F6S & AUS

⁴² 20.05.2021 Partner: AUS

TABLE 5: OPEN CALL 2 EXTERNAL EVALUATORS' COMMITTEE

First Name and Name	Position	Organization
Jenny Camaradou	COVID19 Expert Advisory Panel	NICE – National Institute for Health Care Excellence
Marco de la Feld	Expert evaluator	European Commission
Laura Fiorini	Project Manager and AAL pilot coordinator	University of Firenze
Nuno Seixas	Head of Quality and Operational Excellence	PT Inovação – Altice Labs
Mara Diaconu	Coordinator IDUN project	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Tiago Rua	COVID-19 vaccination: Programme Manager	Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust

1.2.4 OC#2 Results

37 applications have been evaluated as part of the Open Call 2 Stage 2 External evaluation process and 29 were invited to individual interviews. The evaluation committee is rating the best candidates until the end of October 2021, when the results are announced.

The results are not included in this report because they are being communicated to the teams. The final list of funded single and team solutions will be made public after the successful signature of the sub-grant agreements with all entities. At this time, the COVID-X team will produce and disseminate an infographic about the main OC#2 statistics.

2 Community building approach

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant stakeholders is often referred to as 'community building' and is a crucial aspect of COVID-X Programme. During the first project year, the focus on stakeholder engagement was to raise public awareness of the targeted stakeholders in Europe about the COVID-X Open Calls, attracting the top candidates to apply to the COVID-X Acceleration Programme. Once the acceleration programme started, from April 2021 onward, this focus has been enlarged towards optimizing visibility and market impact of the selected COVID-X solutions, the Game Changers.

Moreover, the programme relies on communities, initiatives and projects that will either use the outcomes, relate and, possibly, liaise with its activities along its course. Creating and nurturing an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is always a crucial factor in the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholder's impact on a project depends on its potential power -the ability to influence the value proposition- and the interest in exercising that power.

When it comes to addressing fundamental challenges in Research and Innovation, multiple initiatives often work in a standalone manner to address the same issue from various directions, incurring inefficiencies and being incapable of delivering their full potential. By adopting an open framework of collaboration with peers and target groups that can benefit and contribute to the project's impact, COVID-X will be able to reach a deeper understanding of the requirements and benefits from aligning efforts with similar task forces.

2.1 Agile stakeholder management framework

To maximise the effectiveness of the outreach and community building activities introduced in this document, the COVID-X consortium requires a mechanism for managing systematically the ever-changing list of organisations, initiatives, and players with a position to influence the value streams of the project. For this reason, the programme implemented an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework**, designed to continue developing and strengthening relationships with significant stakeholders through the values of the Agile Manifesto⁴³.

⁴³ Agile Manifesto: <http://agilemanifesto.org/>

FIGURE 20: AGILE STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

This framework for community building works in cycles (see Figure 18), which enables to align the stakeholder engagement with the running project activities and achieve results. Each community building cycle includes three phases:

- **Phase 1 - Scouting.** Considering the expected impact of the programme, this phase focuses on exploring the spectrum of target groups of relevance for the project. The key result is a version of the 'Stakeholder Map', a database to 1) identify target groups -and specific open call candidates within them-; 2) efficiently organise and correlate these stakeholders; 3) define a common terminology to use in all the project's documentation, namely Game Changers, Single Players, Team Players etc.
- **Phase 2 - Interaction.** This stage targets the actual engagement with the stakeholders so that it will be synchronised with the main activities cycles of COVID-X Programme.
- **Phase 3 - Learning.** From the actions performed in the life cycle, the consortium learns lessons that will support the refinement of the next Sprint. Such phase includes insights obtained from consulting stakeholders (e.g. in the form of questionnaires or dedicated interviews), gathering valuable feedback about the project, reviewing the engagement activities performed so far and its impact; a more efficient way to assess the stakeholders, among others.

Moreover, COVID-X Programme covers three main cycles for the community building:

- OC#1 Promotion – from December 2020 until January 2021
- OC#2 Promotion – from June until September 2021
- Reinforcing the impact of the COVID-X Game Changers – from April 2021 until the end of the project.

2.2 Target groups

Promoting the COVID-X Programme and encouraging stakeholders to engage with it, required a common understanding, within the consortia and beyond, which are the project target groups having a remarkable impact on the initiative. Based on the COVID-X Programme objectives and activities, the

consortium has mapped the COVID-X Stakeholders (see Figure 21) including primary and secondary target groups:

- **Primary target groups** cover healthcare and digital service providers that benefit directly from the initiative via the COVID-X Acceleration Programme.
- **Secondary target groups** comprise innovation, health and policy ecosystems and European societies. These groups benefit from the innovative data-driven solutions developed and validated by the primary target groups in the COVID-X Acceleration Programme, accessing the European digital healthcare markets.

FIGURE 21: COVID-X STAKEHOLDERS MAP

The five target groups are briefly introduced below. Further details about the interaction with them will be provided in Section 3.

2.2.1 Primary target groups

The primary target groups benefit directly from the COVID-X Programme and are the main targets of the two open calls organized in 2021: healthcare providers were eligible to join Team Solutions and Digital services providers could apply either as single (validating the solution with one of the COVID-X clinical partners) or team solutions (with a third-party healthcare organization). As part of the programme, these groups obtain direct funding and technical, ethical, and business mentoring to fast-track their solutions on the markets to fight and prevent COVID-19 outbreaks. All solutions joining the acceleration programme are referred as COVID-X Game Changers.

Healthcare providers

This category includes professionals and organizations of the European healthcare system, strongly represented by the clinical partners of COVID-X Consortium (ICH, SERMAS and KI). This group requires more sophisticated technologies and tools to make efficient use of collected COVID-19 patient data to improve care delivery and follow-up of coronavirus patients. Along with three consortium clinical

partners, the COVID-X Programme selects via the two Open Calls and funds around 20 European healthcare providers working with digital service providers (Team Solutions) to provide them clinical data and to validate the innovative data solutions.

Digital Service Providers

This group covers organizations involved in technology innovation, research contribution and business activities highly relevant to the interoperability and application of data-driven technology and AI in the healthcare value chain. The focus is on SMEs and Start-Ups providing data-driven digital healthcare solutions. Their innovation supporting clinical challenges related to diagnosis, prognosis or follow-up of COVID-19 patients should be at TRL7+ passing the level of “Demonstration System” that operates in operational environment at pre-commercial scale⁴⁴. Furthermore, these solutions must have CE marking or close to achieve certification based on the European Medical Device Regulation⁴⁵.

2.2.2 Secondary Target Groups

These groups benefit from the knowledge, innovation, and capacity of 30+ data-driven solutions supported by the COVID-X Programme in the fight against coronavirus. To leverage the impact of the programme, COVID-X consortium is creating synergies with innovation and health ecosystems and widespreading the key innovations of the COVID-X Programme towards the policy ecosystem and society.

Innovation and Health Ecosystems

This group is central in helping to reach out the primary target groups in the different EU regions, contributing to amplify the promotion of the COVID-X Open Calls and the dissemination of the programme results. In the core of this group are digital innovation hubs active in healthcare sector; and to this date, there are 263 DIHs registered in this sector⁴⁶. Another key network is the EIT Health⁴⁷ and its regional nodes.

Moreover, COVID-X is invested in clustering with other European task forces and Horizon2020 projects working on data technologies supporting COVID-19 outbreaks as well as working on more global questions related to pandemics.

Finally, the National Contact Points of H2020 ICT Programmes, and then HEurope Digital and Health Programmes are regularly updated about the opportunities and results from COVID-X Programme.

Society

This group covers patients diagnosed and/or recovered from coronavirus, their anonymized clinical health data supports the healthcare providers to validate and further implement the innovative

⁴⁴ www.cloudwatchhub.eu/exploitation/brief-refresher-technology-readiness-levels-trl

⁴⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/health/md_sector/new_regulations_en

⁴⁶ https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool?p_p_id=digitalinnovationhub_WAR_digitalinnovationhubportlet&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=normal&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_count=1&formDate=1601895423809&freeSearch=eHealth&evolStages=1&evolStages=3&evolStages=5&h2020=false

⁴⁷ <https://eithealth.eu/>

technologies supported in the COVID-X Programme. Therefore, the involved healthcare partners lead the interaction with patients.

In addition, COVID-X encourages a common understanding on benefits that digital care brings to society in the fight against COVID-19, and promotes a secure narrative around Artificial Intelligence. The public is essentially reached out via the project website, in non-specialized media and the dedicated social media channels.

Policy Ecosystem

The European Commission is the backbone of the COVID-X Programme since it is funded under H2020-Coronavirus-2B Call for Proposals. The policy makers and project results contribute to new policies and implement strategies for digital transformation of healthcare – therefore, all key results and outcomes COVID-X Programme will be proactively shared with this group to provide guidance and recommendations for future actions.

3 COVID-X Community

The first COVID-X Programme year has focused on creating the COVID-X Community, including all the stakeholder groups mentioned in Section 2.2, with a varied range of engagement tactics adapted to each target group. The aim of this community is to leverage the impact of the COVID-X Programme beyond the project duration towards all concerned third parties, and, ultimately, to reinforce the market entrance and positioning of the funded innovative solutions tackling coronavirus.

3.1 Engagement Tactics

In alignment with the outreach and dissemination plans of the project (WP3), COVID-X Programme has implemented pre-defined strategies to interact with the different target groups on the methodology. These tactics pursued three main objectives:

- Attract SMEs and Start-ups to apply to the COVID-X Acceleration Programme.
- Bridge the gap between the Digital and the Healthcare sector to create a community to fight against the COVID-19 pandemic in a more effective and faster way.
- Engage with the selected solutions, the COVID-X Game Changers, and support their dissemination towards the digital health markets.

3.1.1 Social Media

Social media channels help to reach a wide audience in a democratic way. Therefore, these channels support easily interact with all the different groups of COVID-X stakeholder. As mentioned in Sections 1.1.2 and 1.2.2, the project has put in place and animates daily 4 social channels, with a major focus on the 2 first ones:

- COVID-X LinkedIn : www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/
- COVID-X Twitter: <https://twitter.com/TheCovidX>
- COVID-X Facebook: www.facebook.com/TheCovidX
- COVID-X YouTube : www.youtube.com/channel/UCZg26pyMWfEUfjiulukh-lg/videos

While COVID-X LinkedIn channel focuses on attracting a more technical audience by posting long professional posts, Twitter aims at reaching a broader public of citizens and patients that could be interested in the topics of healthcare digitalisation and the trustworthiness of AI in medical care, two key topics for all COVID-X related work. COVID-X's Facebook channel was created to have an instant online streaming route for COVID-X webinars rolling out on Zoom. Youtube is used for publishing COVID-X webinars that do not have a restricted target audience.

3.1.2 General Webinars

COVID-X team hosts a series of general webinars essentially to promote the two open calls. Webinars are an effective one-to-many activity having a particular relevance after the COVID-19 outbreak, where most of the conferences, events and on-site workshops were replaced by online versions. They represent a practical and low-cost form of diffusion of knowledge (due to its remote nature) among

the overall COVID-X community. They are a collaborative tool and include polling and question & answer sessions to allow full participation between the audience and the presenters.

As mentioned in Section 1, the project organised **three public webinars in January 2021** to explain the significant objectives of the programme among SMEs and Healthcare providers. This tactic was to attract stakeholders to the OC#1, and **it was again put in place for OC#2 in June and July**, with five different sessions. The webinars outlined what the programme expects from the teams and single solutions to be selected and join the acceleration programme.

In total, **these webinars reached out 400+ participants:**

- OC1 Webinar 1 – 13.01.2021: 100 participants
- OC1 Webinar 2 – 15.01.2021: 80 participants
- OC1 Webinar 3 – 20.01.2021: *participant number not available*
- OC2 Webinar 1 – 22.06.2021: 31 participants
- OC2 Webinar 2 – 23.06.2021: 33 participants
- OC2 Webinar 3 – 24.06.2021: 25 participants
- OC2 Webinar 4 – 13.07.2021: 50 participants
- OC2 Webinar 5 (2nd stage) – 02.09.2021: 72 participants

General webinars explained the application process and gave an overview of the project. They also served to let the participants know who the partners were and explain the Acceleration Programme. In the technical webinars, the partners in charge gave details about the technical requirements, particularly the COVID-X Sandbox. here were also some webinars conducted by the clinical partners, to explain their needs and expectations from the selected single solutions. During those sessions, the participants had the opportunity to raise questions and doubts, addressed by the project partners. The participants were also encouraged to raise any additional questions by email to info@covid-x.eu or through the F6S platform.

3.1.3 Thematic Webinars

All the mentoring sessions of the COVID-X Programme include thematic webinars tailored for the COVID-X Game Changers, designed in a dynamic format to retain participants’ attention and encourage interactions among participants. The sessions are a crucial part of COVID-X Acceleration Programme mentoring methods, and they are delivered by different experts in the domains of the COVID-X partners’ organizations. Table 6 lists the webinars hosted as part of OC1 Acceleration Programme. The OC2 Acceleration Programme Thematic Webinars will be delivered from November 2021 onward.

TABLE 6: COVID-X THEMATIC WEBINARS FROM OC1 ACCELERATION PROGRAMME

Session	Topic	Date	Expert
#1	COVID-X Tech Webinar 1: Monitoring Framework	21.04.2021	Giulio Pagliari, ICH
#2	Data Protection training	06.05.2021	Elena Arredondo and Jose María Laperal, SERMAS
#3	COVID-X Tech webinar 2: Data anonymization with Kibana	19.05.2021	Santiago Barrio and Borja Arroyo, UPM

Session	Topic	Date	Expert
#4	COVID-X Tech webinar 3: Dockerization for software ingestion	02.06.2021	Borja Arroyo and Gustavo Hernández, UPM
#5	COVID-X Business Sprint 1: Customer personas, value proposition	08.06.2021	Milan Steskal, MySugar
#6	COVID-X Tech Webinar 2: Sandbox	23.06.2021	Elena Arredondo and Jose María Laperal, SERMAS
#7	COVID-X Clinical partners & datasets	24.06.2021	Henar Gonzalez, SERMAS
#8	COVID-X Business Sprint 2: Customer Journey Map	07.07.2021	Tamas Békási, EIT Health
#9	COVID-X Business Sprint 3: Healthcare regulations	03.08.2021	Tobias Schreiegg, Siemens Healthyneers
#10	COVID-X Business Sprint 4: Marketing & Growth Funnels	08.09.2021	Tamas Békási, EIT Health
#11	COVID-X big data course 1 - introduction to big data and hadoop (hdfs)	04.10.2021	Jose Antonio Rodríguez, Bosonit
#12	Covid-X Business Sprint 5: Business model	05.10.2021	Henrik Ibsen, Open TeleHealth
#13	COVID-X Business Sprint 6: Risks & stakeholders' mapping	08.11.2021	Henrik Ibsen, Open Tele Health
#14	COVID-X big data course 2 - hadoop architecture, distributed storage (hdfs) and yarn, mapreduce	05.10.2021	Jose Antonio Rodríguez, Bosonit
#15	COVID-X big data course 3 - data ingestion into big data systems (kafka) (1)	06.10.2021	Jose Antonio Rodríguez, Bosonit
#16	COVID-X BIG DATA COURSE 4 - DATA INGESTION INTO BIG DATA SYSTEMS (KAFKA) (2)	07.10.2021	Jose Antonio Rodríguez, Bosonit
#17	COVID-X BIG DATA COURSE 5 - APACHE HIVE	08.10.2021	Jose Antonio Rodríguez, Bosonit
#18	COVID-X Business Sprint 6: Risks & stakeholders' mapping	08.11.2021	Henrik Ibsen, Open Tele Health
#19	Covid-X Business Sprint 7: Financial planning	December 2021	TBD
#20	Covid-X Business Sprint 8: Pitching	January	TDB

3.1.4 Publications

To enable the stakeholders to benefit from the COVID-X Programme results and follow up the project process, the project team communicates about all results openly: the public deliverables are shared on COVID-X Zenodo channel⁴⁸, and uploaded on the project website “news”-section. Moreover, the partners draft and publish articles about the project milestones in different communication channels.

Regarding the Deliverables, all public submitted deliverables are shared with the stakeholders, and for the moment, the following ones can be consulted online:

- D3.1 COVID-X OC#1 D3.1 Outreach material
- D1.1 Ethical and legal framework
- D2.1 Sandbox design & Datalake creation and ingestion
- D2.2 First Sandbox implementation and services provision
- D3.3 COVID-X OC#2 Guidelines

The COVID-X Project has been the scope of different online articles, including:

- BOSONIT website⁴⁹
- WIRED Magazine Italy⁵⁰
- ‘20 minutes’ Spanish Magazine⁵¹
- Research EU Magazine (printed and online versions) - COVID-X Project of the month. ⁵²
- EHCAlliance Website⁵³
- ECHAlliance Website – Online article about the COVID-X Sandbox⁵⁴

Moreover, 10+ online articles have focused on the Open Call 2:

- Enterprise Europe Brussels ⁵⁵
- ECHAlliance Member News⁵⁶
- Digital Health News⁵⁷

⁴⁸ www.zenodo.org/communities/covid-x_h2020

⁴⁹ <https://bosonit.com/en/bosonit-participa-en-covid-x-acelerando-las-soluciones-de-datos-de-covid-19-para-salvar-vidas/>

⁵⁰ www.wired.it/economia/start-up/2021/01/19/intelligenza-artificiale-covid-19/?refresh_ce=

⁵¹ www.20minutos.es/noticia/4555804/0/bosonit-participa-en-el-proyecto-europeo-covid-x-contra-el-coronavirus/

⁵² https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/429472-project-of-the-month-supporting-smes-to-advance-their-solutions-in-the-fight-against-covid-19?pk_campaign=tw

⁵³ <https://echalliance.com/covid-x-programme-unlocking-the-full-capacity-of-artificial-intelligence-and-data-technology-solutions-to-overcome-covid-19-challenges-and-fast-tracking-projects-to-markets-to-save-lives/>

⁵⁴ <https://echalliance.com/funding-collaboration-opportunities-for-member-only-september-2021/>

⁵⁵ www.brusselsnetwork.be/covid-x-funding-acceleration-programme-open-call-2/

⁵⁶ <https://echalliance.com/covid-x-programme-looking-for-data-driven-solutions-to-overcome-covid-19-challenges/>

⁵⁷ www.digitalhealthnews.eu/open-calls/6455-open-call-2-for-accelerating-data-driven-solutions-to-save-lives-from-covid-19

- EU-Startups⁵⁸
- SERMAS website⁵⁹
- STARTUP3⁶⁰
- Systematic Paris Region ⁶¹
- Bio Nanonet Association⁶²
- Call 4Europe Magazine⁶³
- Cluster Lombardo Science della Vita⁶⁴
- Humanitas website⁶⁵

In addition, as detailed in Sections 1.1.2 and 1.2.2, the consortium drafts and publishes in open access regular press releases about the key results and activities to come.

3.1.5 Events

Online and physical events are a great occasion for stakeholder networking and disseminating the project results for wider audiences. However, during the first project year, the COVID-X Programme has been limited in organizing and participating in physical events due to the worldwide pandemic situation and the travel limitations. Sections 1.1.2 and 1.2.2 detail the events where COVID-X partners promoted the running open calls. In addition, in June 2021, BOSONIT and one of the OC#1 Game Changers, TRAJECT, teams participated in 4YFN Event⁶⁶, targeting innovative digital start-ups. During the event, TRAJECT exhibited its solution helping hospitals to manage their patients with a trajectory model of collected health data.

3.1.6 Defining strategies for Community Building

Along with the Agile Stakeholder Framework used for COVID-X Community Building (see Section 2), the COVID-X team has defined a tailored strategy for community building for certain target stakeholder groups, helping the concerned partners to foster together their collaboration in the framework of COVID-X Programme. These strategies (further detailed in Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2.1) focus on community building for:

- COVID-X Game Changers.
- CORONAVIRUS-2B Projects supported by the EC.

⁵⁸ www.eu-startups.com/2021/06/applications-now-open-for-the-covid-x-acceleration-programme-using-data-driven-solutions-to-save-lives-sponsored/

⁵⁹ <https://unidaddeinnovacion.shealth.eu/en/covid-x-2>

⁶⁰ <https://startup3.eu/covid-x-open-call-2-apply-now/>

⁶¹ https://systematic-paris-region.org/appeal_a_projets/covid-x/

⁶² www.bnn.at/covid-x-open-call-2-for-technology-healthcare-providers/

⁶³ www.linkedin.com/pulse/covid-x-acceleration-programme-now-available-using-solutions-europe/

⁶⁴ www.lombardialifesciences.it/news/seconda-open-call-covid-x-per-imprese-e-servizi-di-assistenza-sanitaria/

⁶⁵ www.humanitas.it/news/lai-center-di-humanitas-al-servizio-dellinnovazione-europea/

⁶⁶ www.4yfn.com/

3.2 Targeted engagement actions

Among the COVID-X Community, some targeted stakeholder engagement actions are put in place complementing the other outreach actions carried out as part of the Open Call Campaigns (defined in Section 1).

3.2.1 COVID-X Game changers

The COVID-X technology providers and healthcare providers joining the acceleration programme are called the COVID-X Game Changers. They work together to test and validate the data-driven technologies to be brought on the EU healthcare markets to defeat COVID-19 with the power of data, as illustrated in Figure 22. All COVID-X Game Changers join the Acceleration programme for 10-months, during an onboarding month and three Sprints of three months. All the game changers from OC#1 are listed in Table 4 and the OC#2 game changers are being announced by the end of October 2021.

FIGURE 22: COVID-X PRIMARY GAME CHANGERS BRINGING THE GAP IN HEALTH DATA

Their participation in the COVID-X project focuses on obtaining direct funding and joining the Acceleration Programme, supporting them to nurture synergies with different SMEs, Start-Ups, and healthcare organizations, which could boost their market uptake even further. To foster their community, the COVID-X team has put in place several tailored engagement actions further detailed in the following:

COVID-X partners created [a health map](#), in Figure 23, promoting the participating Start-ups and the clinical sites in the COVID-X OC1 Acceleration Programme. It has been periodically disseminated on the COVID-X social media channels.

FIGURE 23: GAME CHANGERS HEATH MAP

Also, an **online video about OC#1 Game Changers** (see Figure 24) was produced to present to the wide public the funded innovative solutions, the SMEs and Healthcare providers selected within the COVID-X OC1. It is shared openly on the COVID-X YouTube channel⁶⁷ and on the COVID-X website Game Changers-page.

FIGURE 24: VIDEO ABOUT OC#1 GAME CHANGERS

Game Changers-Page on the COVID-X website

The COVID-X website has a dedicated space⁶⁸ for the selected COVID-X Game Changers describing:

67 www.youtube.com/watch?v=10n2P_vyeRM&t=3s

68 www.covid-x.eu/game-changers/

the technological innovation and clinical goal, partner organizations, involved countries and addressed challenges of each onboarded Single and Team Solution. The OC#2 solutions will be added on the webpage during November 2021.

Single Solutions

Team Solutions

FIGURE 25: GAME CHANGERS' WEBPAGE

In addition, as a first step to onboard the selected solutions in the COVID-X Acceleration Programme, the COVID-X partners host a kick-off bootcamp, prior to which the participants receive a **welcome brochure** (Annex 1) describing all key aspects of their participation in the programme, such as communication guidelines for disseminating their project and the EU support, participation timeline and COVID-X team contacts.

FIGURE 26: COVID-X WELCOME BROCHURE:

In April 2021, a **dedicated Pres Release**⁶⁹ about the OC#1 Game Changers was published and shared on Zenodo for all involved stakeholders (see Figure 27). For the moment, it has 68 downloads in open access.

FIGURE 27 PRESS RELEASE FROM APRIL 2021

⁶⁹ [https://zenodo.org/record/4686899/files/COVID-X%20 Press%20Release April2021.pdf?download=1](https://zenodo.org/record/4686899/files/COVID-X%20%20Press%20Release%20April2021.pdf?download=1)

To help people behind the COVID-X Game Changer solutions to connect with each other, AUS created a shared database with the personal **LinkedIn Profiles** of all staff involved in developing the solutions. The aim was to help the teams to create more direct contacts via LinkedIn and encourage one-to-one exchanges.

To support the solutions to communicate about the innovation and disseminate the results of their participation in the COVID-X Programme, the COVID-X team has created **tailored guidelines regarding the external communication** of their project. Furthermore, **relevant forthcoming events** in the field of digital innovation for start-ups and healthcare are scouted and proposed for the teams on a regular basis.

Finally, a dedicated **Community Building Strategy for Game Changers** was created to better align the interaction between the COVID-X team’s and the COVID-X Game Changers. These guidelines (see Figure 28) are addressed to the COVID-X partners helping to set-up a community of the onboarded solutions and teams that follow the 10-month Acceleration Programme, the COVID-X Game Changers. The objective for this community building, to be incentivized by all COVID-X partners, is to foster synergies between the Game Changers, which could give an extra-boost for finding new customers and accessing the digital healthcare markets. The key idea is that the community building is not considered as a separate vertical action, but rather as a horizontal aspect being part of all activities, related to business mentoring, technical support, ethical coaching, and communication, carried out in the COVID-X Acceleration Programme.

COVID-X Programme

Game Changers -
Community Building Strategy

FIGURE 28: COVID-X COMMUNITY BUILDING STRATEGY FOR GAME CHANGERS

3.2.2 Innovation + Health Ecosystems

As detailed in Section 2.2.2, this target group helps to spread out the results and activities of the COVID-X Programme. COVID-X Project has engaged actively with Digital Innovation Hubs, Business Accelerators and incubators, eHealth networks, related European research and innovation projects etc. essentially to widespread the two open calls but also to communicate about the COVID-X Acceleration Programme results. The following sub-sections describe COVID-X’s collaboration with three different clusters that played an important role during the first project half.

3.2.2.1 CORONAVIRUS-2B project cluster

COVID-X Programme is an active player in the European community of 13 projects that run in the framework of Horizon 2020 Coronavirus-2B call funded by the EC (see Figure 29). The goal of the community is to share key outcomes and challenges faced in the different projects.

FIGURE 29: CORONAVIRUS-2B PROJECTS' CLUSTER

The project teams supported the cross-project communication, namely by sharing updates on social media and spreading out the new press releases. In addition, the coordination teams meet regularly online to discuss the challenging topics and results achieved.

Upon a request from The European Commission (EC) (Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology - CNECT.H3) supporting all 13 Coronavirus-2B projects, the COVID-X project developed a dedicated **strategy for building the CORONAVIRUS-2B Projects' Community**. This document is confidential, essentially written for the EC and the COVID-X partners. In this strategy, the COVID-X team defined a set of objectives and target groups for the actions that could guide building and managing this community, especially concerning:

- Connecting the 13 Coronavirus-2B Projects teams.
- Raising public awareness and increasing the visibility of the COVID-X actions at the local, regional, and European scales.
- Implementing, when relevant, cross-project collaboration, especially in shared communication and dissemination actions (such as workshops, webinar, press releases or newsletter).

Sharing knowledge about specific topics and discussing major challenges faced by the other projects, which enables sharing the best practices when dealing with the constantly changing technology and clinical landscape of the coronavirus at the European and the Global levels.

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

STRATEGY FOR THE CORONAVIRUS-2B PROJECTS¹
COMMUNITY

FIGURE 30: STRATEGY FOR CORONAVIRUS-2B CLUSTER

3.2.2.2 PREPARE cluster

COVID-X Project joined the PREPARE H2020 projects cluster in May 2021. This is a group of 12 RIA projects working in the field of emergency situations preparedness and response for countries to cope with unforeseen challenges, such as COVID-19. These 12 projects, with a combined funding of €72 million, have united to form the PREparedness and resPonse for emergency situAtions in euRopE (PREPARE) cluster. This cluster includes the following actions:

TABLE 7: PREPARE CLUSTER ACTIONS

Name of the action	Link
CO-VERSATILE	https://co-versatile.eu/
COVID-X	https://www.covid-x.eu/
COVINFORM	https://www.covinform.eu/
EUR3KA	https://www.eur3ka.eu/
NO FEAR	https://no-fearproject.eu/
PANDEM-2	https://pandem-2.eu/
PERISCOPE	http://www.periscopeproject.eu/
PHIRI	https://www.phiri.eu/
STAMINA	https://stamina-project.eu/
STRATEGY	https://strategy-project.eu/
LINKS	http://links-project.eu/
RiskPacc	https://twitter.com/RiskPacc

FIGURE 31: PREPARE-CLUSTER LOGOS FROM MAY 2021

The main objective of the cluster is to explore synergies, research opportunities, and deliver joint activities to maximise impact of the results. Through mutual support, the cluster will strengthen our response to the ongoing crisis and our aim to be better prepared for future health crises.

The community meets once every two months to share the outcomes of the projects and discuss next steps of the collaboration. Moreover, the COVID-X team published a dedicated online article about the cluster on the project website and social media. In addition, it regularly shares online events, results, and opportunities of these projects (see Figure 32). As a first step of the collaboration, the projects prepared a **common Press Release** shared on the COVID-X website in May 2021⁷⁰.

FIGURE 32: PREPARE CLUSTER ACTIVITY PROMOTION IN SOCIAL MEDIA

⁷⁰ www.covid-x.eu/news/preparedness-and-response-for-emergency-situations-in-europe/

3.2.2.3 ECHAlliance

The European Connected Health Alliance (ECHAlliance)⁷¹ is the Global Health Connector for Digital Health, facilitating multi-stakeholder connections around ecosystems, driving sustainable change and disruption in the delivery of health and social care. Their ecosystem gathers about 850 organizations including government, health & social care providers, leading companies and start-ups, researchers, insurances, patients’ groups, and citizens.

COVID-X project became a strategic partner of ECHAlliance for one year from April 2021 to April 2022 (reimbursing a yearly membership fee). This partnership is advantageous for the project since it promotes its Open Calls and results of the Acceleration Programme for the entire ECHAlliance ecosystem covering 20 000 experts engaged worldwide in the sector of digital health.

As detailed in Section 1.2.2, the COVID-X Open Calls benefitted from several posts in ECHAlliance social media and newsletters. In addition, the structure has published two articles about the first COVID-X programme results, covering the OC#1 Game Changers and the COVID-X Sandbox (see Figure 33 and Figure 34).

FIGURE 33: ECHALLIANCE ARTICLE ABOUT GAME CHANGERS

⁷¹ <https://echalliance.com/>

FIGURE 34: ECHALLIANCE ARTICLE ABOUT COVID-X SANDBOX

3.2.3 The European Commission

The European Commission is considered as a secondary target group of the project, as it funds the innovation activity and in response expects the delivery of the planned results, outcomes, and impact, which contribute directly to the implementation of their political strategy in the field of digital transformation of healthcare and innovation for defeating COVID-19 with health data. The COVID-X project aims at regularly sharing all tangible project results with the EC officers; the COVID-X (F6S) coordinator joins recurrent monitoring meetings organized with the EC teams and joint innovation projects.

Following the principle of open access valued by the EC, all relevant publications will be submitted for Open Research Europe Platform⁷². Furthermore, all deliverables providing project results are submitted to the EC, and all public deliverables are published on the COVID-X website and Zenodo Open Access Platform.

Moreover, the COVID-X Programme was communicated as **the project of the month** in April 2021 in the Research EU Magazine published online and on hard copies by the EC⁷³.

3.2.4 Society

Society, and especially citizens and patients, are considered as a secondary target group of the project. The targeted COVID-X actions aim at encouraging a common understanding of the benefits that digital healthcare brings to society to fight against COVID-19, promoting a secure narrative around the usage of health data and Artificial Intelligence.

⁷² <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

⁷³ https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/429472-project-of-the-month-supporting-smes-to-advance-their-solutions-in-the-fight-against-covid-19?pk_campaign=tw

The engagement strategy towards citizens and patients is currently taking place essentially in social media, and it is adapted to each of the channels: Twitter is used towards a broader audience, while LinkedIn focuses on longer posts that should be more relevant for technical experts. Relevant profiles are monitored within the different social media channels.

Up to the date, **1 573 posts** have been published in the social media channels of the COVID-X Programme (876 on Twitter, 500 on LinkedIn & 197 on Facebook).

The social media channels have raised more awareness and have engaged different targets that follow the last updates of the project.

4 Conclusions

The first half of the COVID-X Programme, from November 2020 until October 2021, has been fruitful in terms of community building, and the project plans to continue following the same agile stakeholder engagement strategy during the second half, from November 2021 until October 2022. The focus of the engagement actions will be shifted from the Open Call promotion to spreading the results from COVID-X Acceleration Programme.

In **social media**, COVID-X channels continue sharing the daily posts engaging citizens, patients, and related experts. The aim is to grow the online community of the project to 6 000+ followers by the end of the project (now the status is 1 020+).

With regards to **publications**, the project continues the stable sharing via its communication channels scientific and technical publications (articles, news items, blog posts) not only about COVID-X project but also about the related technology and healthcare updates. Up to this date 1500+ articles etc. have been shared combined in COVID-X social media channels and the website. In addition, during the second project half, the aim is to publish peer reviewed publications about the technical and clinical research conducted throughout the project.

Four **Press Releases** have been drafted and published, and more will be created and shared with all stakeholders upon achievements of important milestones in the programme. At least three new press releases are foreseen to announce the OC#2 Game Changers as well as key findings and results from the two editions of the Acceleration Programmes (Batch 1 and Batch 2) and regarding the COVID-X Sandbox.

With 20+ **webinars** hosted, the COVID-X team has been very dynamic in organizing general and thematic webinars for the different stakeholders. And more webinars will be hosted: on the one side, a new series of thematic mentoring webinars will be set up for the Batch 2 Acceleration Programme. And on the other side, at least two general webinars will be hosted focusing on showcasing the Game Changer solutions and one webinar about the final release of the COVID-X Sandbox.

The aim is **to grow the COVID-X Community** of primary and secondary stakeholders enabling to widespread the results within the different EU member states, and beyond. Therefore, newer potentially interested target stakeholders will be scouted and reached out regularly via the before mentioned engagement tactics. The team targets to engage especially varied innovation and health ecosystems, helping to participate in more online and physical **events**, especially if the coronavirus-situation enables it.

5 Annex 1 – OC#1 Welcome brochure

Welcome to the COVID-X Programme!

The COVID-X Consortium is happy that your solution & team joined the COVID-X Community, and we will be working together for the next 10 months until January 2022! To prepare you for the COVID-X journey, we have gathered some useful information regarding:

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KICK-OFF BOOTCAMP

To present you the COVID-X Journey, teams & selected solutions, you are invited to take part in the kick-off Bootcamp!

Date & Time: **on Monday, the 12th of April 2021, at 10:30-13:00 CET**

During the online Bootcamp you will meet the COVID-X team and all successful solutions from the Open Call#1. Get prepared to give a 3-minutes pitch about your project & solution! Book the meeting slot now and notice that the meeting access link and agenda will be communicated by mail closer to the event.

To prepare your pitch (3 slides max), please feel free to use the COVID-X slide deck template available here: https://rebrand.lu/COVID-X_Slide_deck_PPT

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

All internal communication takes place in two dedicated channels:

Mailing list: covid-x-oc1-solutions@f6s.com - subscription to the mailing list is mandatory since all official communication will take place in this channel.

Slack Group and Channels: this tool enables to chat easily with COVID-X team and with the other COVID-X solutions as well as access discussion channels dedicated to 3 specific topics: business support, technical questions, and pilots & ethical aspects. To join the COVID-X Slack groups, access the link that will be shared to you by mail.

COVID-X Team Contact points: If you have any questions, doubts, comments, or suggestions regarding the Acceleration Programme, do not hesitate to **contact your mentors!**

Please choose the right mentor according to your inquiry:

- **General aspects** - Alberto Sierra Bañón from BOSONIT (alberto.sierra@bosonit.com)
- **Business mentoring** - Paula Polacenko from CIVITTA (paula.polacenko@civitta.com)
- **Technical support** - Sofia Tsekeridou from INTRASOFT (Sofia.TSEKERIDOU@intrasoft-intl.com)
- **Pilots and ethical support** - Giulio Pagliari from HUMANITAS (giulio.pagliari@humanitas.it)

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3

PARTICIPATION TIMELINE

The funded single and team solutions join the 10-month Programme (April '21 - January '22) with the following key milestones:

Onboarding phase (April21-May21)

Once your proposal has been accepted, you will start the onboarding process. The goal of this phase is to prepare the work to be performed during the acceleration programme, including an initial analysis of the business maturity and needs, matchmaking with the appropriate pilot sites and mentors, and the start of the business development roadmap. Three processes need to be carried out in parallel:

- Definition of the KPIs to be used in project monitoring.
- Contract Preparation and signature.
- Acceleration services tailoring.
- Submission of the full ethics application to the relevant Ethical Committee including the study protocol.

During this period, your team must participate online in various mentoring webinars and/or bootcamp as well as in one-to-one meetings with your mentor team.

At the end of this phase, you will be asked to submit the first deliverable of your project:

D1. Experiment KPIs.

Sprint #1 - (May21-July21)

starts on May 3rd, 2021 and has the duration of 3 months. The project implementation will start in this sprint, and you are required to complete the technical work defined in the work plan provided in your application (Annex 3). The generic goals of Sprint 1 are:

- Complete technical integration with the COVID-X Sandbox.
- Get approval from the Ethical Committee.

During this period, your team must participate online in various mentoring webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Moreover, starting from June, your experiment will be monitored by both clinical (by-weekly basis) and business mentors that will be assigned to your project during the onboarding period.

At the end of this phase, you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project:

D2 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 1.

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4

Sprint #2 - (Aug21-Oct21)

starts on Aug 2nd, 2021 and has the duration of 3 months. You are required to continue with the technical work defined in the work plan provided in the Annex 3 of your application. The generic goals of the Sprint 2 are:

- Validation of the data model.
- Agreement on IP.

During this period, your team must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Additionally, if the COVID-19 restrictions allow, you may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

At the end of this phase, you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project:
D3 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 2.

Sprint #3 - (Nov21-Jan22)

Sprint 3 starts on Nov 2nd, 2021 and has the duration of 3 months. You are required to continue with and finalise the technical work defined in the work plan. The generic goals of the Sprint 3 is:

- Completion of the feasibility study.

As in the previous sprints, your team must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Additionally, if the COVID-19 restrictions allow, you may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

At the end of this phase, you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project:
D4 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 3.

YOUR PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Administrative Documents to be Provided

To finalize the contracting step, we require a set of administrative documents that your team should send through the F6S platform as quickly as possible. In case of questions or doubts, please contact Antonio Damasceno from F6S (antonio@f6s.com).

Connect yourself to the F6S platform and consult the list of required documents and information according to your project type:

- **Single Solutions:** www.f6s.com/covid-xoclcontractpreparation?ref=oclcontractss
- **Team Solutions:** www.f6s.com/covid-x-contract-preparation-team-sol?ref=oclcontractts

Participations

Your team is engaged to join the proposed activities in the framework of the Acceleration Program. All 3 sprints include **webinars, online workshops and other regular meetings** with the mentors. Please notice that in the Sprints 2 and 3, the physical **presence of your team member(s)** might be required for some specific events including the sprint evaluations or events created by the European Commission.

KPIs and Deliverables

By the end of May 2021, your team will set the **key performance indicators (KPIs)** for each Sprint. These KPIs will be defined with the support from your business mentors as these will be validated by the COVID-X team. These metrics will enable the COVID-X team to track your progress in the Acceleration Program.

To define and to report the KPIs and demonstrate your technical progress, your team will draft and submit 4 deliverables (D1-D4):

Table 1 - Reporting timeline

Deadline	Deliverable
31/05/2021	D1 - KPI Definition
30/06/2021	D2 - Sprint 1 Report
31/10/2021	D3 - Sprint 2 Report
31/01/2022	D4- Sprint 3 Report

Reporting, Evaluations and Payment

COVID-X team focuses on evaluating the results (the set KPIs) of your project, the aim is not to monitor the engaged expenditure. The goal is to boost your solution to the markets as rapidly and strongly as possible to save lives!

Therefore, you are engaged to deliver **the set KPIs and deliverables** during the evaluation phase at the end of each Sprint. Once your report is accepted, we ask you to provide **a financial statement**, and the payment is processed upon the reception of this statement.

All reports will be submitted via the F6S platform (www.f6s.com/covid-x). Moreover, the report templates can be downloaded on the same platform.

Table 2 - Payments timeline

Funding (% of budget)	When (in months)	
10%	2	After approval of the KPIs
30%	4	After evaluation of Sprint 1
30%	7	After evaluation of Sprint 2
30%	10	After evaluation of Sprint 3

Open Access

COVID-X Program follows the open innovation policies recommended by the European Commission. Therefore, all non-confidential documents, essentially related to implemented activities, outcomes & communication, are shared online via Zenodo storage cloud (<https://zenodo.org/>). The COVID-X website promotes all public outcomes that are relevant for external stakeholders.

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ACCELERATION SERVICES

COVID-X Programme provides mentoring with the aim to accelerate the final steps towards the market uptake of the top-rated data solutions. From now on, your team will enter this programme with the ambition to streamline the deployment and the techno-economic validation of your solution in the fight against COVID-19. To that aim, the COVID-X partners will provide a wide range of free support services based on your identified and concrete needs, including:

- **Financial** - where your experiment will be granted in direct financial support to advance the technology readiness level of your solutions.
- **Technical support** - Online training and inspirational talks in data-driven technologies. Exclusive capacity building service in new technologies, providing support in the use of the data sandbox and the seamless integration and testing of their services with it.
- **Business Mentoring** - including a service portfolio focused on go-to-market strategies in the eHealth sector, complemented with an investing plan for the most prominent companies.
- **Ethical Guidance** - Supporting Tech Companies to get approval from the clinical ethical committees to deploy the solutions.

Financial Support

During the programme, each selected team will have access to different amount of funding granted:

- **Single Solution Call**: up to €100,000 maximum granted.
- **Team Solution Call**: up to €150,000 maximum granted per consortium, where the maximum financial contribution to be granted to the beneficiaries shall not exceed the amount of €100,000 for SMEs and €50,000 for Healthcare providers.

Technical Support Services

- **Capacity building in new technologies**: A set of available technology courses will be provided by **BOSONIT** experts using an online tool to facilitate access. These courses will be tailor-made to the needs of the selected experiments and will address the main technology areas applied by them.

The total number of courses to be provided is 3 (1 per sprint). Final topics will be defined within the onboarding calls and can include areas such as Data Science, Big Data, RPA, Python, AI, Cybersecurity...

Courses will be delivered online, via Zoom and will have a duration of **8 hours each**. At the end of the courses, participants will be evaluated and will be able to receive a COVID-X Certificate.

- **Sandbox training and support**: Presentation and discussion of the technologies, methodologies and approaches with respect to the deployment and integration of Sandbox related applications. **UPM** and **INTRASOFT** lead these training parts.

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Planned and ad-hoc online discussions highlighting aspects of the containerisation and deployment of apps interacting with the sandbox. Explanation of the offered tools, APIs and ways of engaging with available data. Walkaround the UI components of the platform and related dashboards with introductory information on how to use them. Technical information for API interaction.

This service will be provided on a general basis to all the third parties during the onboarding phase and will be followed up during the mentoring sessions. Individual 1-to-1 mentoring on the Sandbox will be provided if necessary.

Business Support Services

- Mentoring programme:** Mentoring will give you access to specialised expert knowledge that in standard acceleration mostly is unavailable. Experienced experts will provide strategic overview on different topics and provide both business mentoring insights and strategy. The business acceleration programme will cover 8 different business-related topics in general sessions (duration of 1hour + Q&A approx.) and will be delivered monthly. In addition, each topic-specific mentor from a related industry will provide individual consultation sessions for each team after the general sessions have taken place to advise on specific questions and/or concerns that may have arisen.

After the webinars, all the participants will be asked to put in practice the learnings and tasks will be assigned. **CIVITTA** will provide materials and guidelines on how to complete these tasks.

The aim of the mentoring is to create individual business development roadmaps that will be provided at the end of the Covid-X Programme. **CIVITTA will also leverage its pool of knowledgeable business mentors who will be matched on an ad-hoc basis with the teams to support them in tackling more specific business-related topics.**

- Business roadmap definition:** Business development roadmap, in accordance with the mentoring action plan, will be drawn up and delivered at the end of Sprint 3. This will be a live document that identifies the stages of business and technology development needed to be accomplished during the Acceleration Programme.
- Demo Days and workshops:** Workshops and demo days will be organised after each of the sprints (July 2021 (M3), October 2021 (M6) and January 2022 (M9)). The aim is putting together in the same space all the selected projects, together with consortium partners and other relevant stakeholders in order to share experiences, problems and give you the possibility to work with each other and increase the impact and awareness of your solutions. Workshops will be thematic and will be categorised in three main topics: Technical, Clinical and Business.
- Inspirational talks:** Top-notch technical and business experts will host a set of talks. These talks will cover online chats with speakers giving insights about the COVID-19 pandemic & about the start-ups scene around it, including officials from the European Commission (EC) and even showcasing COVID-X solutions. At least 3 inspirational talks per Sprint will be set up making use of online live transmission.

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- Demo moments and Success stories:** COVID-X Program will publicly share the Acceleration Program impact on the project website (www.covid-x.eu) and social media (Twitter & LinkedIn). To collect the stories, the founders will be interviewed, and they fill in an online survey. The major outcomes of each funded project, i.e. success story will be drafted in a short & defined format (following the visual COVID-X brand) during the Sprint 3. Moreover, a promotional video will be produced with video interviews of several participants explaining their solution (objective, status & market perspectives), and the impact of the COVID-X Program on their project.

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RESEARCH PROTOCOL & PILOTS

COVID-X partners will facilitate and create the conditions and environment required by each of the beneficiaries' pilots, either by partner hospitals (ICH, SERMAS, KI) or by external healthcare partners coming from Call for Team Solutions.

The Consortium will help Single and Team solutions in maximizing the impact of the pilots and contribute to the testing and deployment operations as well as market uptake of mature health technologies for the prevention and optimised treatment of the COVID-19 disease.

All pilots will be conducted and monitored with the aim of ensuring a high clinical impact in terms of effectiveness, reliability, quality, precision, accuracy, and rapid response of the tested solutions to overcome the state-of-art achieving better outcomes for patients avoiding overtreatment and under-treatment conditions.

As a reminder, the clinical partners of the COVID-X Team will pursue the following scopes within the project:

- **Istituto Clinico Humanitas (ICH, Italy)** expects to have collaboration with entities to create and validate novel AI-based models with high accuracy for a fast CT scan analysis aiming at supporting the diagnosis of COVID-19 via classification and estimation of the degree of affection. Moreover, this site is interested in development of AI-based solutions for cross analysis between clinical and radiological available data to assess personalized clinical paths and treatment to improve clinical response of classified patients.
- **Hospital Clinico San Carlos (SERMAS, Spain)** expects to have collaboration with entities providing solutions, swiftly and precisely diagnose this condition and assess its prognosis. In particular, the hospital is interested to identify "exceptions to the rule"; i.e. subjects belonging to risk groups but who will fully recover with no or minor complications, and vice versa.
- **Karolinska Institutet (KI, Sweden)** is interested in piloting solutions that enhance the data collection from patients with potential COVID-19 diagnosis, meaning improving the pre-diagnostic processes and clinical pathways with AI based developed components.

The support for the SMEs participating in the pilots will involve following cross-collaboration activities between their single solution team and the appointed pilot sites / with the Team solution team including their healthcare partner:

- **Analysis of feasibility of the solution proposed** - through the definition of a GANTT for goals, KPIs and monitoring the progress of each task.
- **Ethical committee approval for each pilot/solution** - before accessing clinical data and starting the validation phase, each Single or Team solution should get the approval of the local Ethical Committee to ensure that the submitted proposals are compliant with the current legal and ethical regulations.
- **Access to data for third parties** - integration with the Covid-X Sandbox and definition of the data set that the Single or Team solution will need to validate the solution.

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- **Deployment and testing** - through the usage of the Covid-X Sandbox, each Single or Team solution will be able to proceed with the validation of the solution and the accomplishment of the agreed goals.
- **Regular review/monitoring meetings** - during the pilot, Single and Team solutions will be monitored to guarantee the success of the project and discuss the best ways to validate the solutions. Participants will take part in Experiment Progress Meetings (EPs) every two weeks and they will discuss with the clinical mentor the stage of each KPI and identify the new tasks to perform.

Research Protocol

Usually, Clinical partners require the definition of a research protocol and the approval of a local Ethical Committee before starting a research together with a third party. Specifically, the research protocol is a document that describes the project and the basis on which the Ethical Committee verifies the ethical and formal compliance and feasibility.

Since the approval procedure of the research protocol is a crucial step for the beginning of the validation of Single or Team solutions, below we give further information regarding a potential pipeline.

In many cases the Ethical Committee is an independent body and its procedures and regulations may vary depending on the pilot site. Each Clinical Partner will be in charge to give details on timing, documentation and procedures related to the submission of the research protocol. In case of Team solutions and if required, the external beneficiary Hospital or Clinic should give the same type of information and support regarding the submission of the research protocol to their Ethical Committee.

As reported in the Section 4.4 of the Guidelines for Applicants, all the selected Single and Team solutions should get the approval from the Ethical Committee within the end of Sprint 1. Since this process may take up to two months, please start working on the Research Protocol together with the Clinical Partner as soon as possible.

High-level structure of a Research Protocol

This document consists of different sections describing the goals and the design of the pilot project. Usually, the following sections should be filled in:

- Name of the project and main responsible/PI;
- Abstract and rationale of the pilot study;
- Design of the pilot;
- Expected results and timeline;
- Annexes may be requested depending on the local regulations and procedures (e.g. Sub-grant Agreement, etc.).

The approval of the Ethical Committee might be a mandatory document to kick-off the pilot implementation. For this reason, it is crucial to work on the research protocol from the very beginning of your participation in COVID-X. Moreover, the involved clinical partners not only should offer SMEs guidance through the procedures and documentation but should give support regarding contents and deadlines.

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EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Communicate and share your participation in the COVID-X as much as possible in the dedicated channels! To support this, in the annexes, you can find our Communication Guideline.

- Website www.covid-x.eu
- LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/
- Facebook www.facebook.com/TheCovidX
- Twitter [@TheCovidX](https://twitter.com/TheCovidX)

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COVID-X PARTNERS & TEAM

Before the bootcamp, we would like to introduce you to the key COVID-X team that manages the Acceleration Program, the project communication and supports your solution to save lives faster. **Happy to meet you!**

F6S
COVID-X Coordinator & Open Call Manager

Antonio Damasceno
Project Coordinator

Hugo Cantao
Financial Manager

AUSTRALO
Communication and Community

Mona Marill
Project Manager

Blanca Arregui
Communication Manager

CIVITTA
Go-to-market Acceleration Manager

Ronalds Strauhs
Project Manager

Paula Polacenko
Senior Consultant

BOSONIT
Technical Acceleration Manager

Alberto Sierra
Senior Innovation Expert

Miguel Garcia
Director of Innovation

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INTRASOFT

Data integration & management, Data visualization, Sandbox integration

Dr. Sofia Tsekeridou
Senior Research and
Innovation Manager - Expert,
Head of Security & Safety
Lab

Themistoklis Anagnostopoulos
Senior Software Engineer

Serafeim Tsironis
Senior Research &
Development Engineer

EIGHT BELLS

Data protection & security, Sandbox design

Despoina Gkatzoura
Software Engineer and
Project Consultant

Alexandros Karatzos
Software Engineer and
Project Consultant

Universidad Politecnica Madrid

AI and federated learning, Third parties integration

Dr. Frederico Alvarez
Professor and GATV (UPM)
Director

Dr. Gustavo Hernandez
Post-doctoral Researcher

Dr. Silvia Uribe
Post-doctoral Researcher

Humanitas Mirasole

Clinical Partner Italy

Giovanni Angelotti
Lead Data Scientist,
Humanitas AI Center

Carlotta Cattaneo
Business Developer Manager,
Humanitas AI Center

Giulio Pagliari
Project Manager,
Humanitas AI Center

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Servicio Madrileño de Salud
Clinical Partner Spain

Dr. Luis Rodriguez-Rodriguez
Senior Researcher

José Manuel Laperal
Information Security Manager

Elena Arredondo
Innovation Manager

Karolinska Institute
Clinical Partner Sweden

Carl-Johan Sundberg
Professor

Sabine Koch
Professor

Sokratis Nifakos
PhD Student

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COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

This document gives the key guidelines for both internal and external communication activities related to COVID-X Programme. All beneficiaries of the Programme should use the created tools for communication including namely dedicated communication channels & messages as well as the COVID-X branding.

COVID-X in a nutshell

The following text is a short description of the COVID-X Project's objectives and actions. It can be used in different contexts: emails, presentations, social media posts, etc.

COVID-X Programme is a European innovation initiative offering access to funding and to a tailored acceleration programme for start-ups and companies. The objective is to boost the market uptake of AI and data solutions [at TRL7+] to defeat COVID-19 and to save lives. It is supported by the European Commission as part of the response plan to defeat COVID-19 through the power of data.

Through two Open Calls, COVID-X grants 30+ selected companies: [Single Players] obtain 1.000K€ in equity-free funding and get access in technical, business and ethical mentoring as well as in clinical validation at one of the COVID-X pilot sites (in Italy, Spain or Sweden). If the company brings in a Healthcare Provider that can validate their solution, the financial support will go up to 1.800K€ [Team Players]. All selected solutions address challenges related to diagnosis, prognosis or follow-up of COVID-19 patients.

For more information: www.covid-x.eu

Internal Communication

All internal communication takes place in two dedicated channels:

- **Mailing list:** covid-x-oc1-solutions@f6s.com - subscription to the mailing list is mandatory since all official communication will take place in this channel.
- **Slack Group and channels:** this tool enables to chat easily with COVID-X team and with the other COVID-X solutions as well. Once you receive the email to join the team work space, you will find the general channel and the channels dedicated to 3 specific topics: business support, technical questions and pilots & ethical aspects.

COVID-X Team Contact points: If you have any questions, doubts, comments or suggestions regarding the Acceleration Programme, do not hesitate to **contact your mentor!** Please choose the right mentor according to your inquiry:

- **General aspects** - Alberto Sierra Bañón from BOSONIT (alberto.sierra@bosonit.com)
- **Business marketing** - Paula Polacenko from CIVITTA (paula.polacenko@civitta.com)
- **Technical support** - Sofia Tsekeridou from INTRASOFT (Sofia.TSEKERIDOU@intrasoft-intl.com)
- **Pilots and ethical support** - Giulio Pagliari from HUMANITAS (giulio.pagliari@humanitas.it)

Branding

The COVID-X branding includes the fonts, colours, logos and banners that should be used in all COVID-X-related communication.

Project name

COVID-X should be written in capitals and with a hyphen between the D and the X. The full name is **COVID-X Programme** including the Acceleration Programme and access to direct funding.

Font types

Saira: Use in **titles** - download it [here](#).

Abel: Use in **body text** - download it [here](#).

Colour palette

Use colours from the dedicated palette:

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Logo

Please find the **logo** available in this link : https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_logo

If your company wants to add the COVID-X logo to the website, please **link the logo** to the COVID-X website.

Banners

Find the **main banner** available : https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Main_banner

Leaflet

Please find the one-pager here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Leaflet. This leaflet gives a general overview of the programme and it can be freely used for all COVID-X related communication.

COVID-X Website

www.covid-x.eu

The project website

- Gives a general overview of the Program.
- Promotes the open calls and their outcomes.
- Shares updates about COVID-X achievements, including news from solutions.

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- Promotes the COVID-X Community (ie. the funded teams & solutions) towards external stakeholders.

COVID-X team highly recommends promoting the project website as often as possible (in any presentation, social media posts, newsletters, blog posts ,etc.).

Social Media

If your company & team have social media channels, please kindly follow the COVID-X profiles you find below.

When you want to post information about the project on social media, remember to tag COVID-X accounts and also that it is important to talk about it in a concise, informal and positive way, engagingly, and use hashtags where possible in clear and simple language. Innovative and different. Speak personally.

Hashtags to be used: [#TheCovidX](#), [#GameOn](#), [#DebateCovid](#)

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/TheCovidX>

Facebook: www.facebook.com/TheCovidX

LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/

YouTube: www.youtube.com/channel/UC2g28pyMWFEUJiulukh-Ig

Please find some graphics for posting on social media:

- LinkedIn & Facebook graphic is available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_GameChanger_FBandLK
- Twitter graphic is available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_GameChanger_Twitter

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Success Stories

During the programme you will be requested to contribute in a success story, summarising your COVID-X experience at the different phases.

You will be contacted by the Communication Manager sharing with you the main points to be addressed in your post. Moreover, all success stories shall be shared on public communication channels of the project, which enables to showcase **the COVID-X Impact**.

Media Appearance & Follow-Up

During your participation in COVID-CX Programme, **if your solution, team or company achieves any media appearance** (e.g. in social media, newspapers, newsletters, etc), please share this update with the COVID-X Communication Manager so that the COVID-X can leverage this achievement in related activities.

Participation in Videos

During your COVID-X participation, your team can be asked to participate in a video with the goal to share publicly the COVID-X Program achievements. Your participation will be confirmed in advantage with the image rights agreement. Produced video(s) shall be published on the COVID-X website and in the COVID-X YouTube channel. All participants can use it for their dissemination activities.

Events

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If & when your company participates in an event/conference/workshop, etc. and you present/promote your participation in COVID-X project, you should:

BEFORE THE EVENT

1. Inform the communication manager
2. Use the acknowledgement stated below for announcing your participation in the event.

DURING THE EVENT

3. Tweet and mention [@TheCovidX](#)
4. In case you do not have a Twitter account, you should send the text you want to be published on Twitter and some pictures to COVID-X Communication Manager (*see below*)

AFTER THE EVENT

5. Prepare a short written description summarizing your participation in the event.
6. Send the text to the communication manager who will take care of publishing it on the COVID-X website.

Press Release

The COVID-X team issues new press releases as soon as new milestones are met, such as all the solutions are successfully onboarded in the Acceleration Programme. All new PRs will be shared with you.

Please find the latest PR here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_2nd_Press_Release

Newsletters

In case your company is going to release any newsletter including information about COVID-X, please inform the COVID-X Communication Manager that would like to follow all publications.

If you need any graphic or textual input to be used in the newsletter, please contact the COVID-X Communication Manager.

EU logo, acknowledgement and disclaimer

Beneficiaries of EU funding are engaged to acknowledge the support of the European Commission; this is a contractual part of your funding agreement. Please use the acknowledgement template below for your website. It should be visible (preferably on the main page) at least during the contract period.

:

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For any **deliverable** or **document** you may have to hand over, and for any **presentation** you may make, please note that a **disclaimer** is also needed. In law, a disclaimer is a statement denying responsibility intended to prevent civil liability arising for particular acts or omissions. For deliverables, please use the template provided:

For further information about the **EU emblem**, please find the European Commission guidelines available here: (https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf) on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU funding and apply the graphical rules (<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>). The text is displayed to the right, to the left, bottom or up, depending on your needs. There is a choice amongst several fonts to write the text.

COVID-X Communication Manager

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To share your communication updates and to address any question or doubts about the outreach activities or guidelines contact **COVID-X Communication Manager: Blanca Arrogul (AUSTRALO)** - blanca@australo.org

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